

The Kinetic Study of Variation of log k values with respect to different temperature in water-Ethanol media

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Abstract:

The aquo-organic co-solvent used was ethanol in our study. The hydrolysis experiments were carried out at five different temperatures varying from 20°C to 40°C (20°C , 25°C , 30°C , 35°C and 40°C). The specific rate constant values were calculated using the second order equation. In order to highlight the variation of specific rate constant values with gradual addition of organic co-solvent in the solvent mixtures, the values of log k tabulated in Table – I were plotted against mol% of the organic co-solvent. From the Table – II, it is also obvious that in this case, the specific rate constant values are found obeying decreasing trend with decrease in the dielectric constant values of the medium or with the addition of organic co-solvent (ethanol) in the reaction mixture.

Keyword: dielectric constants, electrostatic interactions, ethanol, alkali-catalysed hydrolysis, Barclay-Butler Relationship, unimolecular, bimolecular etc.

Introduction:

Since there are electrical forces between ions and dipolar molecules, and since such forces are modified by the solvent through dielectric constant and polar properties, there should be a dielectric-constant-influenced electrostatic term in a rate expression for an ion-dipolar molecule reaction just as there is such a term in the rate expression for ion-ion reactions. The electrostatic interactions between ions and dipolar molecules will not be so pronounced as in the case of electrostatic interactions between ions and ions, and will therefore be more readily obscured by various other solvent and structural effects. The effect, however, is quite pronounced and should be calculable. Theoretical expression for the influence of the solvent on electrostatic forces which modify rate processes between ions and dipolar molecules have been derived. Some of these theories that we want to mention here are – Laidler-Eyring Equation, Correlation involving Solvent Effects, Bronsted Equation for Acid or Base Catalysed Reactions, Taft's Equation, The Equation of Edwards, The Hanson Equation, etc.

Experimental:

Ethyl alcohol (ethanol) of high degree purity was taken into use. For obtaining ethanol of high degree purity (99.50%) the rectified spirit was purified using ignited Calcium Oxide following the method as described by Vogel².

Ethyl caproate of export quality made in USSR was used. Before its use, it was purified by double distillation method under reduced pressure of 6mm Hg. Its purity was further checked by determining its boiling point which was found to be about 168°C .

Results and Discussion:

The kinetics of alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl caproate was studied in water-ethanol media of varying composition ranging from 20% to 80% (v/v) of organic co-solvent at five different temperature i.e. at 20°C , 25°C , 30°C , 35°C and 40°C . The specific rate constant values were calculated using the second order equation. In order to highlight the variation of specific rate constant values with gradual addition of organic co-solvent in the solvent mixtures, the values of log k tabulated in Table – I were plotted against mol% of the organic co-solvent.

From the plot drawn it is clear that variation of $\log k$ with $mol\%$ of organic co-solvent follows decreasing trend at all temperatures. It is also apparent from the plot that the decrease is not smooth and regular but follows intersecting linear trend at all temperatures. Before 29.25 $mol\%$ of ethanol in the reaction media, the rate of depletion is very sharp at all the temperatures but after 29.25 $mol\%$ of the organic co-solvent in the reaction media, the rate of reaction becomes abruptly slow and smooth. This trend of variation in the values of specific rate constant may be discussed in the light of the views of Parker², Laidler & Landskroener³ and the theory of Hughes and Ingold⁴. According to the theory of Hughes and Ingold, the increase in dielectric constant values of the reaction media results in increase in the rate when there is concentration of charge on the transition state and causes a decrease in the rate when there is diffusion or destruction of charges on the transition state.

In order to study the variation in specific rate constant with dielectric constant of the media, the values of $\log k$ with change in dielectric constant of the media have been tabulated in Table – II. From this table, it is clear that there is decrease in the dielectric constant values of the aquo-ethanol mixtures with the gradual addition of organic co-solvent ethanol in it. In the alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl caproate due to participation of OH^- ion (Negative ion), the negative charge is concentrated on the larger area of the transition state. So, in water ethanol media, the rate of the reaction should decrease with decrease in the dielectric constant of the media according to the Hughes and Ingold theory. From the Table – II, it is also obvious that in this case, the specific rate constant values are found obeying decreasing trend with decrease in the dielectric constant values of the medium or with the addition of organic co-solvent (ethanol) in the reaction mixture. Thus the inferences are in support of the Hughes and Ingold theory⁴ and the views of A. J. Parker². However, many instances which have been reported in the past by Laidler and Lanskroener², D. D. Roberts⁵, Elsemongy et. al.⁶ earlier by Singh & Vineeta et. al.⁷, Singh & Namrata et. al.⁸ and also recently by Anjana & Singh et. al.⁹ and Sushma¹⁰ in which the depletion in the rate has been found in the similar fashion as observed in the present research.

The plot drawn clearly indicates that the rate constant values decrease with different slopes before and after addition of 29.25 $mol\%$ of the organic co-solvent at all temperatures at which the reactions were studied. It is also clear from the plot that with increase in the temperature, the extent of depletion in the specific rate constant goes on decreasing. After all, the depletion in the rate to different extent may be attributed partly due to the dielectric effect and partly due to the solvation effect (solvent-solute and solvent-solvent interactions) which are simultaneously operative in this case of hydrolysis of ethyl caproate in water ethanol media.

Effect of Concentration of Water [H_2O] of the Reaction media on the Rate and on the Mechanism of the Reaction:

The effect of water concentration [H_2O] of the aquo-ethanol mixture, on the rate and mechanism of alkali catalysed hydrolysis of ethyl caproate has been studied in the light of the guidelines and observations reported by Tommila et. al.¹¹, Lane¹² and Elsemongy et. al.¹³.

They have established an idea of the number of water molecules taking part in the formation of activated complex. The number of water molecules

associated with the activated complex is determined by plotting $\log k$ against $\log[H_2O]$. According to the relation proposed by Robertson¹⁴:

$$\log k = \log k_0 + n \log[H_2O]$$

Here, 'n' is the salvation number which tells about the criterion for studying about the mechanism of the reaction.

The values of the $\log k$ and $\log[H_2O]$ have been inserted in Table - III and their plots were drawn. It is obvious from the graph that there are the two intersecting straight lines at each temperature at $\log[H_2O]$ value 1.383 that at different temperatures there are different values of slopes. The values of the slopes of the plots have been recorded in Table - IV.

From the noted values of the slopes it may be inferred that from temperatures $20^\circ C$ to $40^\circ C$, the number of water molecules associated with the activated complex vary (decrease) from 0.733 to 0.227 when $\log[H_2O]$ value is below 1.383 which corresponds to 43.50% water in the reaction media and above 43.50% of water concentration in the reaction media, the number of water molecules associated with the transition state decreases from 1.190 to 0.429 with rise of temperature. Overall, the number of water molecules involved in the activated complex decreases from 1.190 to 0.271 with rise of temperature from 20 to $40^\circ C$.

These observations may be attributed to the fact that equilibrium of water shifts from its bulky form to its dense form with the rise of temperature.

It can also be concluded that at all the temperatures, the number of water molecules associated with the activated complex decreases as the proportion of ethanol increases in the reaction media. The depletion in the number of water molecules with rise of temperature confirms the view of Packer and Tomilinson¹⁵ that ethanol acts as structure builder more when the temperature is higher. Thus, with addition of ethanol in the reaction media, the equilibrium of water is changed from its bulky form to dense form when the temperature of the reaction increases.

As the number of water molecules associated with the transition state or the activated complex go on decreasing with increasing concentration of ethanol in the reaction and also with increasing the temperature of the reaction, hence in the light of the findings of Robertson et. al.¹⁶, it may be inferred that with rise in temperature of the reaction, the mechanistic path followed by the reaction changes from unimolecular to bimolecular with gradual addition of organic co-solvent ethanol in the reaction media. Such inferences have also been found in support of earlier reported findings of Singh & Priyanka et. al.¹⁷ and also of the recently reported inferences of Sunita & Singh et. al.¹⁸ and Sushma & Singh et. al.¹⁹ for the influence of solvent on the mechanistic pathways followed by different solvolysis.

Verification of Barclay-Butler Relationship and evaluation of Iso-kinetic Temperature for evaluating Solvent-Solute Interaction in the Reaction Media:

Barclay and Butler²⁰ have developed an iso-kinetic relationship between enthalpy of activation ΔH^* and entropy of activation ΔS^* as follows:

$$\delta m(\Delta H^*) = \beta \delta m(\Delta S^*)$$

where β is a constant called iso-kinetic temperature and also known some time before as Leffler-Grundwald²¹ solvent stabilizer operator. Leffler⁴¹ has pointed out that plot of ΔH^*

against ΔS^* results in a straight line and the slope of the line and the slope of the line gives the value of iso-kinetic temperature (β). He pointed out that in many solvolysis reactions, the values of slope of the plot of ΔH^* versus ΔS^* comes in between 300 and 400 and this foretells about the considerable interaction between solvent and solute of the reaction mixture.

In the present study, plot of ΔH^* versus ΔS^* from their values mentioned in Table - V has been drawn. The linear plot drawn is in conformity with Barclay-Butler relationship. The numerical value of the slope of the straight line is found to be $323.21 \approx 323.0$ (greater than 300). Thus in the light of Leffler's guidelines, from the values of the slope, it can be opined that there is considerable change in the structure of the reactant or in the solvent or in both the reactant and the solvent due to appreciably strong interaction between solvent and solute present in the reaction mixture (aquo-ethanol media) in the similar way as reported by Leffler²². The structural changes with increasing proportion of the ethanol in water-ethanol media are responsible for the decrease in the specific rate constant values. Similar type of structural changes and solvent-solute interaction in the reaction media have also been reported earlier by Singh & Navendu et. al.²³ and in recent years by Sushma & Singh et. al.²⁴, Narendra & Singh et. al.²⁵ and Ojha & Singh et. al.²⁶.

Conclusion:

Before 29.25 mol% of ethanol in the reaction media, the rate of depletion is very sharp at all the temperatures but after 29.25 mol% of the organic co-solvent in the reaction media, the rate of reaction becomes abruptly slow and smooth. The plot drawn clearly indicates that the rate constant values decrease with different slopes before and after addition of 29.25 mol% of the organic co-solvent at all temperatures at which the reactions were studied. The number of water molecules associated with the activated complex is determined by plotting $\log k$ against $\log[H_2O]$. From the noted values of the slopes it may be inferred that from temperatures $20^\circ C$ to $40^\circ C$, the number of water molecules associated with the activated complex vary (decrease) from 0.733 to 0.227 when $\log[H_2O]$ value is below 1.383 which corresponds to 43.50% water in the reaction media and above 43.50% of water concentration in the reaction media, the number of water molecules associated with the transition state decreases from 1.190 to 0.429 with rise of temperature. It may be inferred that with rise in temperature of the reaction, the mechanistic path followed by the reaction changes from unimolecular to bimolecular with gradual addition of organic co-solvent ethanol in the reaction media. The structural changes with increasing proportion of the ethanol in water-ethanol media are responsible for the decrease in the specific rate constant values.

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Table - I
Variation of log k values of the reaction at different temperatures with mol% of Ethanol in water-EtOH media

% of EtOH (v/v)	Mole% of EtOH	3+ log k values				
		20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C
20%	07.17	2.0722	2.3212	2.5796	2.8189	3.0642
30%	11.69	1.9872	2.2546	2.5298	2.7852	3.0431
40%	17.07	1.9005	2.1903	2.4799	2.7499	3.0198
50%	23.59	1.8243	2.1223	2.4211	2.7112	2.9987
60%	31.06	1.7233	2.0411	2.3646	2.6672	2.9711
70%	41.87	1.6372	1.9678	2.3072	2.6281	2.9489
80%	55.85	1.4998	1.8613	2.2271	2.5698	2.9103

Table - II
Variation of log k values with D (Dielectric constant) values of water-EtOH media at different Temperatures

% of EtOH (v/v)	Mol% of EtOH	20°C		25°C		30°C		35°C		40°C	
		D	3+ log k								
20%	07.17	68.66	2.0722	67.18	2.3212	65.99	2.5796	64.03	2.8189	62.41	3.0642
30%	11.69	62.63	1.9872	61.17	2.2546	59.67	2.5298	58.23	2.7852	56.73	3.0431
40%	17.07	56.49	1.9005	55.16	2.1903	53.78	2.4799	52.44	2.7499	51.08	3.0198
50%	23.59	50.38	1.8243	49.12	2.1223	47.85	2.4271	46.56	2.7112	45.30	2.9987
60%	31.06	44.67	1.7233	43.57	2.0411	42.36	2.3646	41.19	2.6672	40.02	2.9711
70%	41.87	39.14	1.6312	38.06	1.9618	37.00	2.3072	35.94	2.6281	34.88	2.9489
80%	55.85	33.89	1.4998	37.84	1.8613	31.83	2.2271	30.79	2.5698	29.83	2.9103

Table - III
Variation of log k values of the reaction with log [H₂O] values of Water-EtOH Systems (media) at different Temperatures

% of EtOH (v/v)	% of H ₂ O	log [H ₂ O]	3 + log k values				
			20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C
20%	80%	1.6478	2.0722	2.3212	2.5796	2.8189	3.0642
30%	70%	1.5898	1.9872	2.2546	2.5298	2.7852	3.0431
40%	60%	1.5229	1.9005	2.1903	2.4799	2.7499	3.0198
50%	50%	1.4437	1.8243	2.1223	2.4211	2.7112	2.9987
60%	40%	1.3468	1.7233	2.0411	2.3646	2.6672	2.9711
70%	30%	1.2218	1.6312	1.9678	2.3072	2.6281	2.9489
80%	20%	1.0458	1.4998	1.8613	2.2271	2.5698	2.9103

Table - IV
Values of the slopes of the plots of log k versus log [H₂O] at different Temperatures

Temp. in °C	Slope - I when log [H ₂ O] value is below 1.383	Slope - II when log [H ₂ O] value is above 1.383
20°C	0.733	1.190
25°C	0.582	1.005
30°C	0.424	0.789
35°C	0.333	0.520
40°C	0.227	0.429

Table - V
Variation of ΔH^* , ΔG^* and ΔS^* values of the reaction with mol% of EtOH in Water EtOH media

% of EtOH (v/v)	Mol% of EtOH	ΔH^* in kJ/mol	ΔG^* in kJ mol at 30°C	ΔS^* in J/K/ mol at 30°C	$\Delta S^* + 50$ in J/K/ mol at 30°C
20%	07.17	85.2	87.01	-05.97	44.03
30%	11.69	90.57	87.30	10.79	60.79
40%	17.07	95.88	87.59	27.36	77.36
50%	23.59	101.43	87.93	44.55	94.55
60%	31.06	106.49	88.26	60.02	110.02
70%	47.87	112.77	88.59	79.80	129.00
80%	55.85	121.70	89.06	107.72	157.72